

Human Factor in the Media Space of Modern Society and States

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role of the human factor in the media space in modern societies and states. The issues of the rapid development of Media and Technology, their impact on the structures of society and the state, how the human factor is formed in the media space and achieving efficiency through new approaches are studied.

Also analyzed were information security problems and new approaches to solving them, special laws, regulations and international cooperation. The role of social media platforms in shaping public opinion and their monitoring and analysis approaches have been examined. Data on algorithms and control systems were collected to prevent misinformation from spreading. Approaches to the educational system for the development of media literacy, digital literacy courses and community campaigns were studied. The data found was analyzed and synthesized. The main problems and approaches in each direction were identified, and their significance and results were evaluated.

Keywords: modern societies, media space, human factor, information security, digital literacy, false information, social media, public opinion, monitoring, analytical tools, algorithms, control systems, media literacy, data protection

INTRODUCTION

Today, the media space, that is, information and communication technologies and mass media, has become very important for modern societies and states. The Internet and social media platforms have further enhanced the influence of the human factor by facilitating information dissemination and communication. How quickly and widely spread information, its content and reliability play a big role in this. Along with the expansion of opportunities for obtaining and distributing information, there is also an increase in false and incorrect information. This further increases the role of the human factor in the media space and encourages them to use new approaches.

the media space, the human factor basically has three main roles: information production, information distribution and information reception. These roles include journalists, bloggers, social media users and the average citizen. In these processes, the content, quality and impact of information depends on the human factor, through which society and states interact.

METHODOLOGY

This article describes the methodological approaches used to analyze the role of the human factor in the media space in modern societies and states. The article contains reports and recommendations of international organizations such as UNESCO, the UN and the European Union on information security and media literacy, scientific articles written on the topics of information security, social media and public opinion, and media literacy, literature and

scientific articles, national and international laws on ensuring information security and regulations were studied.

MAIN PART

In the media space, the human factor plays a key role in the processes of information distribution, reception and analysis. Journalists and media workers as information producers determine the quality of information. Their level of professionalism, adherence to ethical standards and independence ensure the reliability of information. Social media users actively participate in the information dissemination process and contribute to the rapid spread of information.

Speaking about the human factor in these processes, it plays a key role in ensuring **information security in the media space of modern societies and states**, controlling social media that plays a key role in **shaping public opinion, and promoting and ensuring media literacy** .

First , information security is one of the urgent issues for modern societies and states. The reliability and accuracy of the information disseminated in the media space plays a decisive role in ensuring the public's trust in the information. The human factor is important in this process, and the actions and decisions of each person involved in the process of information dissemination and reception are an important factor in ensuring information security.

Dissemination of incorrect or false information can lead to chaos and distrust in society. These situations have a negative impact on economic, political and social decision-making. For example, during a pandemic, misinformation has fueled vaccine resistance and undermined health systems. Also, the dissemination of incorrect information during the election period increases distrust in the election results and leads to political instability.

Therefore, new approaches should be used to ensure information security. One of the most important approaches is to improve digital literacy. Digital literacy gives people the skills to analyze information, evaluate sources, and spot false information. One of the ways to reduce these problems is to introduce digital literacy classes in the education system and educate different segments of the population.

When we talk about ensuring information security, control of information distribution processes is one of its important factors. Cooperation between the states and the private sector is needed here, because states must introduce special laws and regulations, and these laws must ensure the accuracy of information, limit the spread of false information, and provide for serious penalties. For example, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) adopted in the European Union is important in ensuring information security. GDPR helps people gain more control over their data by setting international standards for personal data protection. This law introduces strict rules aimed at ensuring the security of personal data and preventing their illegal use, and at the same time, GDPR imposes new data protection obligations on international organizations and companies, which encourages the development of new approaches and strategies in the field of information security.

Also, ensuring information security through international cooperation is of great importance in the modern world. Since information security is a global issue, it is necessary to strengthen information exchange and cooperation between countries and international organizations. Adherence to standards and protocols adopted by international organizations plays an important role in ensuring information security.

It should also be said that information security is important for modern societies and states, and the role of the human factor, digital literacy, control of information dissemination processes, and international cooperation is important in this regard. Through these approaches, it is possible to ensure information security and establish a reliable flow of information in society.

Second , social media has become a powerful tool in shaping public opinion with its wide-ranging and rapid information dissemination capabilities. Social media platforms, such as

Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and others, allow information to be shared and discussed quickly with a wide audience. In this process, the human factor plays a big role, and the quality and content of the information distributed by each user, blogger or journalist shapes public opinion.

The quality and credibility of information shared on social media platforms has a significant impact on public opinion. People actively participate in social networks by expressing their opinions, sharing news and discussing, and at the same time, the rapid spread of incorrect or false information is also a major problem in the process. This can lead to the wrong formation of public opinion, social instability and mistrust.

Media has become a space for people to experience emotions and behavior as a source of experiences that affect the way they think, the type and intensity, while through the media people get various news and information, which undoubtedly affects the way they form relationships with different people in their lives. Modern mass media is not only a source of entertainment and information, but the media provided by the mass media allow viewers to adapt themselves to the modern world, accelerate changes in education, sensitize them to culture and help them form social connections.

Currently, the media space shapes worldviews and attitudes that influence human activity. Media space influences the process of family integration. The family spends time together while receiving media messages. By spending free time in front of the TV or on the Internet, individual family members can learn about each other's interests, find common topics for conversation, and share ideas about the content they watch, which strengthens family ties and builds identity. However, the media can also contribute to family breakdown. Modern technologies cause household members to close themselves off and private worlds are formed, that is, each family member creates a private world for himself on social networks and begins to live in it, which leads to loosening of ties and mutual limitation of communication with other family members. Such a phenomenon can have a serious negative impact on the correct social and moral development of children and young people

It is necessary to develop new approaches to the above-mentioned problems, and for this we give the following suggestions.

important approach is to use social media monitoring and analytics tools. Through social media monitoring, public and private organizations can monitor the mood and opinions of the community in real time, and through this, they can identify important issues that affect public opinion and take the necessary measures. For example, during election campaigns, through social media monitoring, voters' opinions and moods can be monitored, and election strategies can be adjusted.

Second, with the help of analytical tools, it is possible to analyze a large amount of information and determine their trends. These tools provide detailed information on how widely information is shared on social media platforms, as well as user reactions and opinions. The state and society should use these tools widely so that they can rely on real and accurate information when making important decisions.

At the same time, it is necessary to introduce special algorithms and control systems to prevent the spread of false information through social media platforms, and with the help of these systems it is possible to detect and prevent the spread of false information. For example, platforms such as Facebook and Twitter have introduced systems to detect false information using special algorithms, delete them or warn users. Through such approaches, it is possible to ensure a reliable flow of information on social media platforms.

Social media is of great importance in the formation of public opinion, and in this process, the human factor, the use of monitoring and analytical tools, the introduction of algorithms and control systems to prevent the spread of incorrect information, and the improvement of media literacy are important approaches. Through these approaches, the state and society can rely on reliable and accurate information to make important decisions.

Thirdly , media literacy is considered as an important and necessary approach for modern societies. The acceleration of the global information flow, the widespread use of digital technologies and social media platforms create the need to develop the skills to assess the quality of information and to develop proper analysis. Media literacy plays an important role in developing people's ability to correctly receive, analyze and use information in the media space.

For this, it is necessary to introduce and widely promote media literacy classes in the educational system. These lessons teach students the skills to analyze information, assess its credibility, and identify false information. Young people and students can make the right decisions in the media space, evaluate the sources of information and check their reliability. Also, Media Literacy teaches young people to analyze information while verifying it . Through this process, people have the opportunity to review information with a critical eye, determine its content and purpose, verify sources, and assess the reliability of information. Information analysis skills help people identify and avoid false or manipulative information.

By teaching young people to check and analyze information, we can develop the skills to detect false information in them. Fake news has become a big problem of modern societies. Through these skills, people will be able to verify the reliability of information, identify sources of false information and avoid spreading it. Preventing misinformation is important to maintaining trust and stability in society.

The flow of information can be vast and complex, and media literacy develops people's skills in navigating this flow of information, identifying relevant and reliable information, and using it appropriately. Through this process, people can find their direction in the flow of information and have the opportunity to receive the necessary information quickly and efficiently.

In order to improve media literacy, it is necessary to introduce not only classes in schools and universities, but also to develop the skills of correct analysis and evaluation of information among the older population through public campaigns promoting media literacy. Such campaigns can be carried out through social media, television and other media, and at the same time, by organizing special courses on the Internet and digital technologies, it is possible to increase the digital literacy of the population and teach them the skills to evaluate information correctly.

Media literacy is important as a new approach for modern societies. Through this approach, people develop the skills to correctly receive, analyze and effectively use information. By introducing media literacy classes in the educational system, promoting media literacy and organizing digital literacy courses, it is possible to ensure reliable and quality information flow in society.

The most important thing for education today is to form people so that they can live in the conditions of modern civilization and solve the tasks before them. Mass media undoubtedly bring a new quality to our lives: they make it easier to establish and maintain social relationships and act due to their immediacy, accessibility and abundance of information, tools and functions. However, if they are not used carefully, all the advantages can turn into disadvantages. The opportunities and threats of mass media presented in this article require continuous analysis, especially the development of solutions that address the negative consequences of mass media exposure . In order to become a conscious participant in virtual reality, it is necessary to remember not only the basic security rules for identity and data protection, but also to properly filter information, maintain a balance between the use of online and offline tools, and strengthen online etiquette and critical thinking skills. Given that media events have profound, often irreversible, effects on their audiences, the youngest recipients need to develop their own media literacy. “Relevant and systematic media education for children, youth and parents is the only chance for social progress in the media space.

CONCLUSION

For modern societies and states, the human factor in the media space is of great importance. Through information security, public opinion, media literacy and new approaches, this process can be managed effectively. Representatives of the state and society, as well as every citizen, should be active and responsible in the media space, and the role of the human factor, its responsibility in the processes of information production, distribution and reception should be further increased, and new approaches should be introduced to ensure the reliability and quality of information in the media space.

Effective and responsible use of media space serves the stability of society, the quality of life of people and the development of civil society. Truthfulness and reliability of information, openness and constructiveness of communication, quality and comprehensiveness of education are the main requirements of the media space. A deeper understanding of the role of the human factor in the media space and its impact on society is important for everyone in modern society. Thus, the media space is recognized not only as a means of information dissemination, but also as an important platform that ensures active participation of people and enriches society.

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